

External insertion, competitiveness, and the growth of the Brazilian economy (1999–2021): theory and empirical evidences

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Abstract

This paper aims to estimate the income and price elasticities of Brazil's exports and imports with the United States, the Netherlands, and China across 12 sectors, based on the multisectoral Thirlwall's Law. Using an ARDL model and seasonally adjusted quarterly data from 1999 to 2021, the analysis reveals that the income elasticities are more robust, positive, and statistically significant in many cases, consistent with the literature. Brazil shows greater competitiveness in basic food and beverages with the U.S. and in industrial inputs and transport equipment with the Netherlands, while demonstrating low competitiveness in several industrial sectors in relation to China. Additionally, the country faces difficulties in the fuel, processed food, and semi-durable goods sectors in its trade with the U.S. and the Netherlands. The results highlight the importance of sectoral policies focused on the most competitive sectors as a strategy to promote long-term growth compatible with external balance.

Keywords: Multi-Sectoral Thirlwall's Law, International Trade, Economic Growth, Competitiveness, Brazilian Economy.

JEL Classification: C22; F14; F43.

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1. Introduction

The discussion about long-term economic growth is a topic that has accompanied economic science since its inception. Various theories have been developed to explain the phenomenon, highlighting factors such as the endowment of productive resources, human capital, total factor productivity, institutional quality, capital stock, aggregate demand, trade openness, industrialization, and export complexity.

The difficulty in isolating factors in macroeconomics contributes to the lack of definitive answers, as multiple factors tend to act simultaneously. A classic example is the growth of Japan and the "Asian Tigers." These countries exhibited strong industrialization, high education levels, respect for contracts, trade openness, and state planning, especially in promoting technological exports. Such characteristics make it difficult to identify a single primary factor as a determinant of growth.

In the Brazilian case, the possible deindustrialization and re-primarization of the export basket have been discussed in recent decades. In the 2000s, the debate was inconclusive: while some authors denied this process (such as Nassif, 2008), others (like Oreiro and Feijó, 2010) pointed to clear signs of this trend. By the 2010s, the data became more evident: in 2019, Brazil began to export more basic products than industrial ones for the first time in 40 years (Martello, 2020), and the share of technological goods in exports dropped to its lowest level in 24 years (Chiara, 2020).

The major question now is whether this re-primarization compromises long-term growth. For some classical approaches, the type of product exported does not matter. However, other theories argue that specialization in products with greater complexity and technological content is essential for development (Rodrik, 2006; Hidalgo and Hausmann, 2009).

This paper is based on the hypothesis that the composition of the export basket is crucial for growth compatible with balance of payments equilibrium (BP), according to Araujo and Lima (2007). The empirical analysis uses ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) models, with quarterly data from 1999 to 2021, to measure the income and price elasticities of Brazilian export and import demand in relation to three trade partners: the United States, China, and the Netherlands. Exports were disaggregated into twelve groups, according to the Classification by Major Economic Categories (CGCE). The aim is to identify, by goods group and partner, where Brazil shows greater dynamic competitiveness, i.e., a higher ratio between income elasticities, which favors growth with external balance

This article is divided into three sections, in addition to this introduction and final remarks. The second section provides a summary of the literature review, while the third presents the methodology of the empirical exercise. The fourth section presents

and discusses the results and is subdivided into three parts, each devoted to one of the countries analyzed (the USA, China, and the Netherlands).

2. Literature Review on Trade, Growth and Balance of Payments Constrained Growth

Since the foundation of economics as a separate discipline, economic growth has been a central topic of discussion. Smith, when inaugurating the modern study of economics, highlighted the importance of the division of labor, economies of scale, market size, and the integration of nations into international trade, which fosters this process. However, the author focused on the absolute advantages between countries, meaning the cost in different locations to produce the same product. In the lowest-cost location, production would tend to occur and be exported to others.

Contrasting this idea, Ricardo developed the theory of comparative advantage. According to this theory, what matters is the relative cost of producing different goods. A nation will always be more productive (in relative terms) in some sector. Productive specialization in sectors where the country has comparative advantages will lead to greater consumption of all goods, as it allows for importing (and consuming) the relatively more expensive goods in larger quantities than would be possible in an autarkic economy. For Ricardo, what each country produces is not relevant, and trade is beneficial for all nations involved.

Regarding Ricardo's theory, Lavoie (2014) raises some objections to the assumptions. Some of these include full employment and full utilization of productive capacity, the implicit mechanism that guarantees balance in the trade balance, and the absence of increasing returns in activities. Prasch (1996) also criticizes the lack of externalities, free mobility of capital and labor between countries, the idea that physical capital does not cross borders, and the assumption that economic resources are fixed. Other criticisms, such as those made by Learner (1994, cited in Prasch, 1996), include perfect competition, identical technologies, trade without cost, the same number of goods and factors, and uniform tastes among consumers in different countries.

An extension of the Ricardian model is the one developed by Heckscher-Ohlin (hereinafter HO), in which the authors consider two inputs in the production process, capital and labor, and assert that countries would specialize in the production of goods that use the factor they have in relative abundance, importing products that are intensive in the other factor. The model has been modified by several authors who sought to incorporate stylized facts into its structure, such as import tariffs and immobility of factors, but many of the criticisms made to Ricardo's model also apply to the HO model.

The HO model predicted the equalization of factor prices between countries. Since the marginal return of factors is decreasing, countries with an abundance of labor should have higher marginal returns on capital and attract investments from wealthy countries. However, Lucas (1990) found that internal savings and investment are quite

close, meaning that current account balances are approximately balanced. This contradiction became known as the Lucas Paradox, explained by the immobility of factors, political risk, and weak institutions.

Many other neoclassical models have been developed and empirically tested, although few have become consolidated. Among them, the model by Grossman and Helpman (1989) stands out, which presents a model with two countries, endogenous technological progress, and three sectors: final goods, intermediate goods, and R&D. In this model, trade and industrial policies affect long-term growth. Comparative advantages can be acquired or natural, breaking with the static nature of previous models.

Neoclassical models evolved and incorporated elements such as trade barriers, economies of scale, imperfect market structures, and information asymmetries. Major international economics textbooks, such as Krugman et al. (2018), already incorporate these elements. However, external constraints, the importance of demand, and the assumption of full employment are still present. Neoclassical models argue that trade is beneficial and should be free, with state intervention only to correct market failures.

However, Chang and Andreoni (2016) report attempts by economists such as Rodrik, Lin, and Stiglitz to incorporate principles of industrial policies into the neoclassical framework. Rodrik and Hausmann emphasize the need for the state to provide public goods and coordinate investments, while Lin proposes guidelines for selecting sectors to be fostered. Cherif and Hasanov (2019), in an IMF study, show that countries successful in industrial policies combine support for sophisticated sectors, export orientation, and intense competition.

Despite these examples, the mainstream still maintains that the best policy is free trade and that the productive structure is endogenous, shaped by institutions and human capital, with the state not playing a role in inducing industrialization. In contrast, the Keynesian tradition developed theories linking international trade and economic performance.

Thirlwall's Law (1979) developed a model in which growth is driven by demand but constrained by the country's ability to generate foreign exchange, i.e., by the balance of payments. As imports increase with income, the product cannot expand indefinitely without creating external imbalances. The author argues that price elasticity has little effect and that the central determinant of growth is the ratio between the income elasticities of exports and imports. The growth rate is given by the rate of growth of exports divided by the income elasticity of imports.

However, the original model only considered goods, ignoring services, capital flows, and interest payments. Therefore, Thirlwall and Hussain (1982) expanded the model by incorporating capital flows and found that these allowed developing countries to grow faster than predicted. Later, Moreno-Brid (2003) added interest payments and

the sustainability of external debt. Santos and Silva (2017) included unilateral transfers, which are important for very poor countries.

The version used in this paper is the adaptation by Araujo and Lima (2007), which is based on a Pasinetti model and considers different trade partners and sectors, disaggregating elasticities. The Multi-Sector Thirlwall Law (MSTL) shows that sectoral competitiveness and the composition of the trade basket are decisive. Growth may accelerate if the country expands the share of sectors and markets in which its elasticity ratio is favorable. According to Batista and Neder (2020), “The country may experience an increase in the income growth rate even when the world income growth rate does not occur, which is conditioned on changes in the sectoral composition of exports and/or imports.”

Keynesian models, by emphasizing demand and the balance of payments, justify policies such as capital controls, tariffs, quotas, aggregate demand management, and industrialization. Although it does not require export growth to come from industry, the low-income elasticity of primary products indicates that productive diversification tends to accelerate growth. More recently, the approach of economic complexity, proposed by Hidalgo and Hausmann (2009), has gained prominence as a predictor of growth.

Gouvêa and Lima (2013) use the Multi-Sector Thirlwall Law (MSTL) to investigate whether Brazilian economic growth between 1962 and 2006 was restricted by the balance of payments (BP), with special attention to the II National Development Plan, a period during which efforts were made to explicitly alter the production structure to sustain growth. Using data on Brazilian GDP, world GDP, real exchange rate, and sectoral foreign trade data, and applying the Johansen cointegration test due to the I(1) integration of the variables, the authors found, in the aggregated version of the LT, income elasticities of 2.021 for exports and 1.613 for imports. The price elasticities were 0.902 (exports) and -2.542 (imports). In the multi-sector version, the income elasticities of exports were significant at 1% in all 18 sectors analyzed, with positive highlights for metallurgy and machinery and equipment (elasticity ratios above 3), and negative ones for rubber and plastics, textiles, oil, and fuels (ratios below 0.5). Only two sectors showed significant price elasticity for exports, compared to 15 for imports. Comparing actual growth with estimates from the conventional LT and MSTL, the tests indicated empirical adherence, reinforcing the external constraint hypothesis. OLS and rolling regression analyses revealed an increase in export elasticity around 1973 and a decline in import elasticity between 1985 and 1994, associated with the oil sector. Between 1974-1984, the elasticity ratio improved, but there was a reversal starting from 1994-95.

Santos (2014) applies the MSTL using GMM-Difference and GMM-System methods to bilateral trade between Brazilian states and China (1999-2009), segmenting goods into basic, semi-manufactured, and manufactured. The bilateral real exchange rate is adjusted for inflation differentials. The results indicated income elasticities of

Chinese demand for Brazilian goods of 0.584 (basic), 0.614 (semi-manufactured), and 0.57 (manufactured), all significant, while the price effect was lower, ranging from 0.15 to 0.2. For imports, the exchange rate was not significant, but the income effect impacted all three segments: 0.476, 0.538, and 0.247, respectively. The elasticity ratios were above 1 for all groups, with a highlight for manufactured goods (2.3). However, despite the relatively good performance of manufactured goods, they accounted for only 20% of exports in 2009, compared to 70% for basic goods. Brazilian imports from China, in turn, were 98% manufactured. The author suggests diversifying the export basket to expand the share of industrial goods in the Chinese market and also examines dynamic sub-sectors in the Kaldorian sense, linking productivity and external demand.

Silva, Hermida, and Santos (2014) also use the GMM-System method to estimate the MSTL in trade between Brazilian states and Argentina and the USA between 1995 and 2010, dividing goods into the same three groups. Brazil had an elasticity ratio above 1 in all three segments in both relations, with highlights for manufactured goods (1.544 with Argentina and 1.384 with the USA). Disaggregated analyses of 20 sub-sectors revealed high competitiveness in sectors such as aerospace and aeronautics (high technology), food and beverages (low technology), and shipbuilding (medium-low technology), all with ratios above 1.8 in trade with Argentina. With the USA, the positive highlights also included the refined oil and fuels sector (1.76). Only metallic products recorded a ratio below 1. The authors conclude that the industry is the most dynamic sector to stimulate growth compatible with external balance and suggest policies prioritizing sectors with higher competitive potential.

Dias (2015) estimates the LT and MSTL for Portugal (1994-2013), using the Two-Stage Least Squares method to deal with income endogeneity. In the aggregated version, the income elasticity was 2.32 (exports) and 2.24 (imports), with insignificant price elasticities. The elasticity ratio (1.61) implied a predicted growth of 1.31%, close to the actual growth. In the multi-sector version, with weighting by 17 sectors, the estimated growth was 1.35%. Portugal was more competitive in machinery and equipment (ratio 2.49) and less in vehicles and transport (0.54). Agricultural imports had an income elasticity of 3.73, and exports of plastics and rubber had 2.84, but there was no significance on the opposite side of trade, making it impossible to calculate the ratio.

Silva and Almeida (2016) incorporate the concept of Global Value Chains (GVCs) into the MSTL, applying the GMM-Difference and GMM-System methods to the Brazilian transport equipment sector (1996-2011). Using a global input-output table involving 40 countries and 35 sectors, the authors consider domestic value added in exports and the distinction between goods integrated or not in GVCs. The results showed that currency devaluations increased exports (elasticities between 0.66 and 0.8) but also increased imports due to productive complementarity. The income elasticities of exports ranged from 1.076 to 1.283; for imports, they reached up to 1.5. All elasticity

ratios were below 1, even for goods integrated into GVCs, pointing to a dynamic disadvantage for Brazil.

Lima Júnior and Silva (2018) test the MSTL by incorporating infrastructure investments, especially those made under the Growth Acceleration Program (PAC), for Brazilian states between 2008 and 2013, using panel models (pooled, fixed and random effects). The goal is to assess whether investments in highways generated positive spillovers on manufacturing exports. For imports, the pooled model indicated higher income elasticity in states with greater penetration of imported goods, while the exchange rate was not significant. Only for manufactured goods did investments significantly impact demand. For exports, the fixed effect was chosen for industrial goods, and the exchange rate had the opposite signal than expected. The income elasticity was significant at 1%, and infrastructure investments were significant and positive only for manufactured goods. Since the effect on exports exceeded that on imports, the authors conclude that PAC contributed to the external competitiveness of the manufacturing sector, being an important tool for a multi-sectoral growth strategy.

Batista and Neder (2020) analyze 69 countries with low and middle income (World Bank classification) between 2000 and 2013, using GMM-System to test if actual growth is consistent with MSTL predictions. Goods were categorized according to Lall (2002) into primary, resource-based, low, medium, and high technology. Incomes were treated per capita, and lagged data on trade and real exchange rate were included. The results indicate that the price elasticity of exports was not statistically significant, but other coefficients were as expected.

Teixeira and Missio (2021) estimate the MSTL via GMM-System for Brazilian states between 1998 and 2014, using state GDP per capita, the average GDP of partner countries, and the real exchange rate, as well as segmenting trade into five groups (high, medium-high, medium-low, low technology, and non-industrial goods) with 19 sub-sectors. Exports presented significant income elasticity above one in sectors such as aircraft and vehicles, while price elasticity was only significant for primary products. For imports, the exchange rate had an unexpected positive signal, while income elasticity was significant in most sectors, with highlights for aircraft (4.07), pharmaceuticals (1.5), railways (2.23), and fuels (1.47). The growth predicted by MSTL (4.64%) surpassed actual growth (3.66%). The highest elasticity ratios were observed in sectors such as optics (2.174), the automotive industry (2.161), recycled goods (2.989), and textiles (3.325).

Blecker (2016) addresses recurring critiques of the Balance-of-Payments-Constrained Growth model. He responds to contentions such as the alleged implicit assumption of similar growth rates for exports and imports, the imprecise influence of world growth on national export performance, the debate between the level and the rate of change of the exchange rate in determining growth and trade elasticities, and the applicability of the model to smaller economies. The latter

critique is especially relevant because supply-constrained models often assume that smaller economies face infinitely elastic demand for their goods.

Thirlwall (2012) traces the genesis of his seminal model, presents several empirical studies that have tested its core proposition, and reasserts his conviction that external trade remains a fundamental constraint on the growth of developing nations. Consequently, he emphasizes the necessity of both expanding exports and implementing policies designed to reduce the income elasticity of demand for imports.

Drawing upon the multisectoral versions of the Balance-of-Payments-Constrained Growth (BPCG) models, this study analyzes the elasticity ratio for Brazil concerning three prominent trade partners. These partners are: the United States, which was Brazil's largest trading partner until recently; China, currently the main partner; and the Netherlands, which is home to Europe's largest port and serves as a major distribution hub for the European continent.

3. Empirical Approach and Dataset Description

For the calculation of income elasticities of demand for exports and imports for the product groups, the three largest destinations of Brazilian exports in 2021³, were selected: China, the United States, and the Netherlands, with respective shares of 28.7%, 10.7%, and 3.51%. The Netherlands, although relatively small in share, serves as a proxy for Brazilian trade with European countries, particularly the Eurozone, as it hosts the largest port in Europe and many products are re-exported from there.

The export and import data were obtained from ComexStat, provided by the Federal Government, on a monthly basis. These data were deflated monthly using the U.S. Consumer Price Index (CPI), sourced from the Federal Reserve Economic Data (FRED). The data were seasonally adjusted using the X-13 method in Eviews10. Since the method does not accept zero data, some series were lost in the process, preventing the estimation of the corresponding elasticities.

The segregation of exported and imported goods was done according to the Classification by Major Economic Categories (CGCE) Level 2, provided by ComexStat. The categories are:

1. Basic food and beverages, mainly for industry;
2. Processed food and beverages, mainly for industry;
3. Capital goods, except industrial transport equipment;
4. Durable consumer goods;
5. Semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods;

³ Excluding Argentina, discarded due to the lack of continuous quarterly GDP data and monthly inflation data since 1999, which prevents estimation in a comparable manner to the other countries.

6. Other unspecified goods;
7. Basic fuels and lubricants;
8. Processed fuels and lubricants;
9. Industrial transport equipment;
10. Basic industrial inputs;
11. Processed industrial inputs;
12. Parts and accessories for capital goods;
13. Parts for transport equipment.

After seasonality adjustment, the monthly data were summed to obtain quarterly results, as the effect of income on the demand for imports and exports was calculated using the GDP of the countries, which is released on a quarterly basis. For Brazil, GDP data were sourced from IBGE, while for the U.S., China⁴, and the Netherlands, they were sourced from FRED.

To differentiate the income effect from the price effect, the bilateral real exchange rate with trading partners was also used. For the U.S., China, and the Netherlands, the nominal exchange rate was taken from IPEADData, while the price indices were extracted from FRED. The exception is Brazilian inflation, for which the IPCA was used and directly sourced from IBGE, for later deflation of the exchange rate. The real exchange rate was calculated on a monthly basis and then averaged quarterly for use in the estimations.

The elasticity ratio for each trading partner and product group was calculated using natural logarithm variables, through the ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model, taking the long-term coefficient in the case of cointegration.

Some advantages of the ARDL, which influenced its choice, include the generation of long-term coefficients (provided the variables are cointegrated) and the automatic determination of lags by an objective criterion (in this work, the Akaike criterion), reducing the researcher's degrees of freedom when estimating the model and searching for results. In summary, the equation estimated by the ARDL was as follows:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha_0 + \delta_1 y_{t-1} + \delta_2 x_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_1 \Delta y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_2 \Delta x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

where y is the dependent variable, x is the independent variable, α_0 is the constant, Δ represents the first difference, δ are the long-term parameters, and Φ are the short-term

⁴ The Chinese GDP was the only one available without seasonal adjustment. The adjustment was also made using the X-13 method in Eviews10.

parameters. Here, the focus is on the long-term parameters for the income elasticity of demand for imports, which will be used to calculate the elasticity ratio.

The estimated equation was for the group of imported and exported goods against GDP (to capture the income effect) and the real exchange rate (to capture the price effect), with a restricted constant, as per the following equations

$$X_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \delta_1 X_{ij,t-1} + \delta_2 PIB_{t-1}^* + \delta_3 Câmbio_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_1 \Delta X_{ij,t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_2 \Delta PIB_{t-i}^* + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_3 \Delta Câmbio_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

$$M_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \delta_1 M_{ij,t-1} + \delta_2 PIB_{t-1} + \delta_3 Câmbio_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_1 \Delta M_{ij,t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_2 \Delta PIB_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \Phi_3 \Delta Câmbio_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

where: α_0 is the constant, δ is the short-term coefficient, Φ is the long-term coefficient, PIB is the GDP of the trading partner, PIB is Brazil's GDP, i is the trading partner, j is the sector, and t is the time period.

Since there are three trading partners and 12 product groups (excluding group 6, which consists of unspecified goods), 36 models for exports and 36 models for imports were estimated, totaling 72 models. All models had the same specification, but due to the absence of data, some could not be estimated. Only those that presented a significant negative error correction mechanism (ECM), cointegration, parameter stability, and significant income elasticity were reported.

The maximum number of lags allowed was 6 periods (one and a half years) for both independent and dependent variables, and the Akaike criterion was used to select the most appropriate model. Conventional tests for autocorrelation (LM) and heteroscedasticity (BPG) were conducted and are reported in the annex, as well as the selected model. In the case of autocorrelation, the treatment was done with the HAC matrix, while for those that violated the homoscedasticity assumption, the White matrix was used, in both cases with a 5% significance level. To verify stability, the CUSUM and CUSUM² tests were performed.

In many cases, it was not possible to estimate the elasticity ratios due to the lack of statistical significance in the income elasticities of certain product groups, which also occurred in other works, such as in Neder and Batista (2020), where the authors attempted to estimate export and import functions for several countries.

4. Empirical Results and Discussion

4.1. Brazil X United States Trade

The United States ceased to be the largest market for Brazilian exports in 2009 and the main source of imports in 2021, with China taking the lead. Still, the U.S. remains a key partner for Brazil, occupying the second position.

The table below summarizes the estimated price and income elasticities for bilateral imports and exports between Brazil and the United States.

Table 1 – Elasticities of Brazil X United States Bilateral Trade Calculated for the Period 1999-2021

Country	Income Elast.	Prob.	Price Elast.	Prob.	Obs	Adjustments
G1 Exp USA	3.02	0.0001	-1.09	0.0028	91	-
G2 Exp USA	1.16	0.0126	0.24	0.3376	88	-
G3 Exp USA	1.13	0.0363	-0.50	0.1620	88	Dummy 2005–2015 to stabilize the model
G4 Exp USA	-1.53	0.0201	1.59	0.0000	90	-
G5 Exp USA	-1.37	0.0001	0.93	0.0000	90	-
G8 Exp USA	-0.82	0.4550	1.24	0.0170	90	-
G10 Exp USA	1.96	0.0000	-0.08	0.3429	88	Dummy 2016–2021 to stabilize the model
G11 Exp USA	1.81	0.0005	0.20	0.4239	87	-
G13 Exp USA	0.00	0.9926	-0.42	0.0315	86	Dummy 2010–2012 and 2016–2019 to stabilize the model
G2 Imp USA	1.89	0.0000	-1.44	0.00	88	-
G4 Imp USA	1.97	0.0066	-1.05	0.0070	88	Dummy 2011–2014 to stabilize the model
G5 Imp USA	1.43	0.0000	-0.55	0.0000	87	Dummy 2006–2014 to stabilize the model
G7 Imp USA	5.63	0.0000	0.48	0.3941	87	Dummy 2013–2016 and 2019–2021 to stabilize the model
G9 Imp USA	1.73	0.0429	-1.63	0.0023	90	-
G10 Imp USA	1.71	0.0001	-0.29	0.2595	88	-
G11 Imp USA	1.70	0.0000	-0.22	0.0961	86	Dummy 2015–2017 and 2018–2019 to stabilize the model
G12 Imp USA	0.45	0.6488	-0.74	0.0629	86	-

Source: Results obtained by the authors from Eviews 10

Only the estimates that showed statistical significance in income and/or price elasticity were reported. Models with unstable parameters, which could not be adjusted with dummies, as well as those without cointegration, were not presented.

For group 1 (basic food and beverages, mainly for the industry), the income elasticity of exports was significant, with a very high coefficient (3.02), significant at 1%. According to the estimated coefficient, a 1% increase in the U.S. GDP is associated with a 3% increase in Brazilian sales of this group of goods to the U.S. On the export side, this segment has the highest income elasticity. For this sector, the long-term price competitiveness was also relevant but with a negative coefficient (-1.09) and significant at 1%, which is unexpected. This indicates that depreciations of the Brazilian real discourage exports of these goods to the U.S. On the import side, neither income elasticity nor price elasticity were significant and, therefore, were not reported.

For group 2 (processed food and beverages, mainly for the industry), the income elasticity of exports drops significantly to 1.16, while the income elasticity of imports becomes significant, with a coefficient of 1.89. Dividing the two, we get the elasticity ratio of 0.61, indicating low Brazilian sector competitiveness compared to the U.S. Thus, for this sector and commercial partner, Brazil has growth potential that is compatible with a trade balance deficit with the U.S., reflecting competitive weakness in a slightly more sophisticated sector. On the price elasticity side, only the Brazilian demand for American products was significant, with a high coefficient, significant at 1%, and with the expected negative sign (-1.44). A positive aspect for the sector is that exchange rate depreciation may reduce Brazil's dependency on U.S.-produced goods in this segment.

For group 3 (capital goods, excluding industrial transport equipment), only the income elasticity of exports was significant, with a coefficient of 1.13 and significant at 5%. On the import side, there was no significance in the income elasticity. Price elasticity was not significant in any of the cases.

Groups 4 (durable consumer goods) and 5 (semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods) presented unexpected results, with a negative relationship between U.S. income and demand for Brazilian products, or a negative income elasticity of demand, which is theoretically usually justified for inferior goods, though it is difficult to justify here with the classification used. In the first case, significance was found at 5%, while in the second case, it was at 1%. On the other hand, the price elasticity came as expected, with a positive sign (real depreciation increasing sales to the U.S.) and significant at 1%. The coefficients were high, 1.59 for group 4 and 0.93 for group 5, indicating the significant role of price competition in these industrial segments.

Regarding the income elasticity of demand for imports, the results came as expected. For each 1% increase in Brazilian GDP, demand for durable consumer goods increases by 1.97, and demand for semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods increases by 1.43. Price elasticity was also significant in both cases, with the expected

sign, where a fall in the dollar is associated with an increase in imports of both groups. The price effect on demand was more relevant for durable goods (-1.05) than for semi-durable and non-durable goods (-0.55), both significant at 1%.

In group 7 (basic fuels and lubricants), the income elasticity of Brazilian demand for American goods was significant at 1%, with the highest coefficient of all in bilateral trade (5.63). The irrelevance of price and the growing dependence on American goods in this sector highlights the importance of Petrobras' investment policy, which could reduce external dependence and increase Brazilian income, compatible with a balance of payments equilibrium, while ensuring national energy security.

For group 8 (processed fuels and lubricants), only the price elasticity of exports was significant, with a positive coefficient (1.24) and significant at 5%. Thus, price competitiveness is important for the insertion of Brazilian products in the U.S. market, but not American income growth. This may be due to these goods having low differentiation, where price is the main competitiveness factor, not extra price competition.

For industrial transport equipment (group 9), both income elasticity (1.73) and price elasticity (-1.63) were high and significant only for Brazilian demand for American goods, but not the other way around.

Looking at basic industrial inputs (group 10), both the income elasticity of exports (1.96) and imports (1.71) were significant at 1%, resulting in an elasticity ratio of 1.146, favorable to Brazil, indicating a slight dynamic national advantage in this segment. On the other hand, price elasticities were not statistically significant.

For group 11 (processed industrial inputs), the results are similar to those in the previous group. The income elasticity of exports was 1.81, and imports were 1.7. Thus, the coefficients were very close to those in group 10, and consequently, the elasticity ratio was 1.065. Statistical significance was also found at 1% for both income elasticities. The difference with basic industrial inputs is that for processed inputs, the price elasticity of demand for imports from the U.S. was relatively low, but as expected (-0.22), and statistically significant at 10%, whereas for the previous group, the significance was not verified.

Goods in the category of parts and accessories for capital goods (group 12) presented statistical significance only at 10% for the price effect on Brazilian demand for American goods, with a coefficient of -0.74, also as expected. Income elasticities were not statistically different from zero, nor was the price elasticity of U.S. demand for Brazilian goods. Finally, group 13 (parts for transport equipment) showed statistical significance only for the price effect on exports, with a negative sign opposite to expectations (-0.42), and significance at 5%. Thus, a real appreciation would increase exports, which is difficult to theoretically defend.

From the analysis above, we find that Brazil's dynamic competitiveness compared to the United States, analyzed by the income elasticity of export demand, is highest for basic food and beverages (3.02), followed by basic industrial inputs (1.96), indicating a competitive advantage in low-tech goods. On the opposite side, the income elasticity of Brazilian demand for U.S. goods is highest in the basic fuels and lubricants sector (5.63), indicating an opportunity that can be addressed by domestic production, with investments from Petrobras. The income elasticities for food and beverages (processed) and durable consumer goods produced in the U.S. are high (above 1.8), although well below the basic fuels and lubricants group.

4.2. Brazil–China Trade

China has become increasingly relevant in Brazil's bilateral trade since the 2000s, reaching the position of Brazil's largest export market and main supplier of imported goods. This scenario makes bilateral analysis crucial, as it allows us to understand the sectors in which Brazil is able to insert its products into the Chinese market and vice versa, as well as the competitiveness dynamics that influence long-term growth and trade balance equilibrium.

However, an important limitation was identified: the database used for this analysis lacked data for groups 1 and 2 (basic and processed food and beverages), making it impossible to estimate elasticities for these segments — which are of great importance to Brazil–China trade.

The following presents the results of the long-run elasticity estimations for the segments that showed statistical significance, calculated using the ARDL model, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – Brazil–China Bilateral Trade Elasticities (1999–2021)

Country	Income Elast.	Prob.	Price Elast.	Prob.	Obs	Adjustments
G3 Exp China	1.64	0.000 0	0.40	0.418 5	91	Dummy 2009–2015 and 2018–2021 to stabilize the model
G4 Exp China	-0.73	0.475 1	-2.80	0.054 9	88	Dummy 2008–2021 to stabilize the model
G5 Exp China	2.31	0.000 0	0.89	0.047 7	87	CUSUM ² not stable, but parameters appear consistent
G10 Exp China	1.62	0.000 0	-1.13	0.206 0	88	-
G11 Exp China	0.75	0.010 2	0.92	0.279 9	87	Dummy 2005–2017 to stabilize the model

G12 Exp China	-0.09	0.532 4	-0.91	0.000 3	86	-
G3 Imp China	7.60	0.000 0	-0.72	0.020 6		CUSUM ² not stable, but parameters appear consistent
G5 Imp China	6.50	0.000 0	-1.20	0.000 0	89	Dummy 2009–2020 to stabilize the model
G10 Imp China	6.29	0.000 0	0.43	0.134 7	86	Dummy 2007–2011 to stabilize the model

Source: Results obtained by the authors from Eviews 10

The first group that showed statistical significance in the income elasticities of both export and import demand was the capital goods group, excluding industrial transport equipment (group 3). We can clearly see the low competitiveness of Brazil vis-à-vis China in this segment. The estimated income elasticity for exports was 1.64, compared to 7.6 for import demand elasticity, resulting in an elasticity ratio of 0.216. This indicates that Brazil would grow just over 20% of what China grows, considering external balance, if the elasticity ratios of the two countries followed those of this sector. It is clear here that Brazil is unable to compete in this segment with the Chinese industry. Furthermore, the real exchange rate was not significant enough for Brazil to increase its market share in China, but the depreciation of the real reduced imports of these goods from China (with a coefficient of -0.72, significant at 5%).

The durable consumer goods segment (group 4) did not show significant income elasticity, only the price elasticity of demand for exports, but only at the 10% level, with a coefficient showing an inverted sign (-2.8). This indicates that a depreciation of the Brazilian currency reduces exports of these goods to China, which is difficult to justify theoretically. However, this result was not obtained when using the more commonly applied 5% statistical significance threshold.

For group 5 (semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods), we again see Brazil's low ability to compete with Chinese products during the analyzed period. The income elasticity for exports was 2.31, compared to 6.5 for imports (both significant at 1%), resulting in an elasticity ratio of 0.356, also very unfavorable to Brazil. The increase in Chinese-produced consumer goods sold in Brazil was intense during the period from 1999 to 2021, highlighting the competitive weaknesses of the national industry. On the other hand, the price effect was found to be significant for competitiveness in this product group. Each 1% increase in the real Yuan/Renminbi exchange rate was associated with a 0.89% increase in exports of semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods to China (significant at 5%) and a 1.2% decrease in the entry of Chinese products into Brazil (significant at 1%).

Brazil is also uncompetitive in relation to Chinese companies in the basic industrial inputs segment. It is notable that the estimated income elasticity for exports

was 1.62, while for imports it was 6.29, both significant at 1%, resulting in an elasticity ratio of 0.258. The price elasticity of demand, both for imports and exports, was not significant in this sector, indicating that competitiveness in this market relies primarily on non-price factors.

For group 11 (processed industrial inputs), changes in Chinese products were associated with changes in Brazilian exports, with a coefficient of 0.75 and significance at 5%. Thus, Chinese demand was found to be inelastic with respect to income for this segment of higher-value-added Brazilian industrial goods, but statistically significant. However, the price elasticities and the income elasticity of Brazilian demand for Chinese processed industrial inputs were not statistically different from zero.

Finally, the goods that make up parts and accessories for capital goods (group 12) also showed statistical significance only for Brazilian sales aimed at the Chinese market, not the other way around, and only for the price effect, but with an inverted sign (negative, -0.91) compared to what was expected, and significant. This indicates that the appreciation of the exchange rate increases exports of these industrial goods to China.

We observe that Brazil faces serious competitive issues with respect to Chinese products. The strong growth of China during the period made it the largest buyer of Brazilian products and supplier to the domestic market, but it exacerbated Brazil's competitive weaknesses in several segments. In the three sectors where it was possible to calculate the elasticity ratios (capital goods, semi-durable and non-durable consumer goods, and basic industrial inputs), we observed that the income elasticity of Brazilian demand for Chinese goods is very high, always above 6, much higher than the income elasticity of Chinese demand for Brazilian goods, resulting in elasticity ratios that are very unfavorable to Brazil. This shows that when Brazilian income increases, much of the extra demand leaks abroad, especially in these segments and for industrial products produced in China, undermining our ability to grow rapidly with external balance.

4.3. Brazil–Netherlands Trade

The last country analyzed is the Netherlands, the largest destination for Brazilian exports in Europe in 2021, in addition to having the busiest port on the continent and representing the gateway for Brazilian products and the exit point for European products destined for Brazil. Thus, the Netherlands plays a significant role in Brazilian trade and is analyzed in this subsection, with the main results summarized in Table 3, following the methodology presented earlier:

Table 3 – Elasticities of bilateral trade Brazil X Netherlands calculated for the period 1999-2021

Country	Incom e Elast.	Prob.	Price Elast.	Prob.	Ob s	Adjustments

G10 Exp NLD	3.64	0.023 4	-2.94	0.000 0	86	-
G13 Exp NLD	4.75	0.000 0	0.80	0.034 6	91	Dummy 2011 to 2015 to stabilize the model
G2 Imp NLD	2.18	0.032 9	-0.28	0.740 5	91	-
G3 Imp NLD	1.11	0.000 8	-0.60	0.033 5	91	Dummy 2009 to 2012 and 2013 to 2015 to stabilize the model
G5 Imp NLD	2.37	0.000 0	-0.62	0.002 1	91	-
G8 Imp NLD	9.64	0.000 0	0.15	0.914 3	91	Dummy 2004 to 2006 and 2006 to 2015 to stabilize the model
G11 Imp NLD	1.61	0.001 5	-0.05	0.805 7	90	Dummy 2008 to 2021 to stabilize the model
G12 Imp NLD	0.69	0.072 9	-0.51	0.064 0	88	-

Source: Results obtained by the authors from Eviews 10

Bilateral trade between Brazil and the Netherlands presents the peculiarity that the elasticities that were statistically significant come from different sectors when analyzing exports and imports. This means that the Brazilian goods exported to the Netherlands are different from the Dutch goods entering Brazil when there are changes in income and exchange rates.

On the export side, two groups showed significant elasticities: basic industrial inputs (group 10) and parts for transport equipment (group 13). Analyzing group 10 first, we observe a high-income elasticity of Dutch demand for Brazilian products, with a coefficient of 3.64 and statistical significance at 5%, indicating an opportunity for external insertion. However, the exchange rate result came in the opposite direction of expectations, with a highly negative coefficient (-2.94), statistically significant at 1%.

In group 13, the income elasticity was even higher than the previous case (4.75), with significance at 1%, also indicating strong Brazilian dynamic competitiveness. Here, the price elasticity was also significant (0.8), with significance at 5%.

Now, analyzing the sectors with significant elasticities in the opposite direction, for Brazilian demand for Dutch goods, we first have group 2, consisting of processed food and beverages, mainly destined for the industry. For these goods, only the income elasticity was significant (2.18), with significance at 5%. The price elasticity, however, was indistinguishable from zero.

For capital goods, excluding industrial transport equipment (group 3), we observed significance for income elasticity (1.11), the lowest among the estimable elasticities in bilateral trade, and price elasticity (-0.6), significant at 1% and 5%, respectively. Here, the price effect occurred in the normally expected direction, with a depreciation of the real reducing demand for foreign goods.

Durable and non-durable consumer goods (group 5) also showed significant income elasticity of demand (2.37) and price elasticity (-0.62), both significant at 1%, with expected signs.

The group with the highest income elasticity of Brazilian demand for Dutch goods is, by far, the group of refined fuels and lubricants (group 8). The income elasticity was 9.64, significant at 1%, while the price elasticity was indistinguishable from zero. This income elasticity of demand was the highest recorded, both for imports and exports, in Brazilian trade with the three countries analyzed. Thus, Brazil's dependence on imported fuels and lubricants is being exacerbated, and the leakage of domestic consumption to such an extent reduces long-term economic growth compatible with external balance. To reverse this situation and reduce national dependence, increasing domestic supply is of utmost importance. The resumption of investments and expansion of installed capacity through Petrobras is one possible way to activate the internal supply chain.

Refined industrial inputs (group 11) showed significant income elasticity of demand at 1% and a coefficient of 1.61, but the price elasticity was not statistically significant. Finally, group 12 (parts and accessories for capital goods) showed both price elasticity and income elasticity significant only at 10%, with coefficients in the expected direction (-0.51 and 0.69, respectively). Both the price and income effects were weak but statistically significant, although only when the confidence interval was expanded.

In the estimations made, we observe that the income elasticity of Dutch demand for Brazilian goods is high in the two groups that showed statistical significance (above 3.5 in both), indicating strong Brazilian competitiveness in basic industrial inputs and parts for transport equipment. On the other hand, when the Brazilian economy grows, the demand for refined fuels and lubricants imported from the Netherlands increases substantially (income elasticity above 9), indicating an opportunity for the national industry and for an energy policy that reduces external dependence, improving Brazil's elasticity ratios. In this specific sector, price elasticity was not relevant, showing that an active extra-price competition policy is necessary to gain competitiveness. The income elasticity of Brazilian demand for Dutch goods was also high in the sectors of processed food and beverages and durable and non-durable consumer goods, with price elasticity being relevant only for the latter group.

5. Final Remarks

This paper uses the Thirlwall multisector model to estimate the income and price elasticities of Brazilian external demand between 1999 and 2021, based on twelve sectors defined by the Classification of Major Economic Categories (CGCE) and three trading partners: the United States, China, and the Netherlands. The goal is to identify the sectors and markets in which Brazil exhibits the highest dynamic competitiveness, which could inform a growth strategy compatible with the balance of payments (BP) equilibrium.

The results point to erratic behavior of the price elasticity. In many cases, it is statistically insignificant, and when significant, its signs vary. This is not surprising, as it is common in empirical studies for price elasticity to be low or indistinguishable from zero. However, it is observed that the exchange rate has a greater impact on reducing imports than promoting exports, especially in this study.

On the other hand, the income elasticity presented more consistent results, with high and statistically significant coefficients for sectors and countries with which Brazil has more intensive trade relations. This highlights the importance of income adjustment for external balance, as predicted by the theory.

Specifically, Brazil showed dynamic competitive advantage in the sectors of basic food and beverages for the United States and basic industrial inputs and transportation equipment for the Netherlands. In contrast, performance against China was weak: the income elasticity ratios were below 0.5 in all sectors with statistical significance. The country also showed low competitiveness in the sectors of processed food and beverages and semidurables with the Netherlands, as well as strong external dependence in the sectors of fuels and lubricants, revealing opportunities for the development of domestic productive capabilities.

These findings indicate that sectoral policies focused on areas where Brazil already has competitiveness — or where there is greater demand leakage — could be low-cost strategies to foster sustainable growth. Additionally, the weak response of exports to exchange rate variations suggests that adjustments via exchange rate are insufficient; external adjustment mainly occurs via income.

Finally, structural transformation of supply and strengthening of exports are essential to overcome the limits imposed by the balance of payments and generate a virtuous growth cycle.

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Anexos

Annex 1: Cointegration F-Statistic and Error Correction Mechanism (ECM)

	F-Statistic	Critical Values				Cointegration	ECM	
		I(0) Bound		I(1) Bound			(Prob.)	
		10%	5%	10%	5%			
G1 Exp USA	4.20	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.309140 (0.0001)	***
G2 Exp USA	10.95	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.666271 (0.0000)	***
G3 Exp USA	4.49	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.238692 (0.0000)	***
G4 Exp USA	5.72	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.228956 (0.0000)	***
G5 Exp USA	5.91	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.233378 (0.0000)	***
G8 Exp USA	6.81	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.449894 (0.0000)	***
G10 Exp USA	8.67	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.938697 (0.0000)	***
G11 Exp USA	3.77	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Inconclusivo	-0.190545 (0.0002)	***
G13 Exp USA	3.13	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Inconclusivo	-0.200317 (0.0006)	***
G2 Imp USA	8.78	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.571550 (0.0000)	***
G4 Imp USA	4.83	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.228397 (0.0000)	***
G5 Imp USA	13.21	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.619206 (0.0000)	***
G7 Imp USA	7.51	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.644209 (0.0000)	***
G9 Imp USA	4.14	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.409101 (0.0001)	***
G10 Imp USA	9.50	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.620760 (0.0000)	***
G11 Imp USA	4.46	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.438127 (0.0001)	***
G12 Imp USA	4.48	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.085278 (0.0000)	***
G3 Exp China	9.77	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.680895 (0.0000)	***
G4 Exp China	4.89	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.207359 (0.0000)	***
G5 Exp China	3.76	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Inconclusivo	-0.329649 (0.0002)	***
G10 Exp China	2.87	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Inconclusivo	-0.143100 (0.0009)	***
G11 Exp China	3.12	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Inconclusivo	-0.158383 (0.0006)	***
G12 Exp China	10.64	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.291206 (0.0000)	***
G3 Imp China	6.70	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.365931 (0.0000)	***
G5 Imp China	15.99	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.497412 (0.0000)	***

G10 Imp China	6.11	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.472246 (0.0000)	***
G10 Exp NLD	6.38	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.203937 (0.0000)	***
G13 Exp NLD	8.33	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.577205 (0.0000)	***
G2 Imp NLD	4.19	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.286669 (0.0001)	***
G3 Imp NLD	16.88	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.839173 (0.0000)	***
G5 Imp NLD	6.28	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.395873 (0.0000)	***
G8 Imp NLD	15.68	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.824986 (0.0000)	***
G11 Imp NLD	5.76	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.469128 (0.0000)	***
G12 Imp NLD	4.18	2.63	3.1	3.35	3.87	Sim	-0.297264 (0.0001)	***

The symbols *, ** and * denote rejection of the null hypothesis at the 1%, 5%, and 10% significance levels, respectively.

Source: Results obtained by the authors from Eviews 10

Annex 2: Lags selected in the models by the Akaike criterion, LM Autocorrelation Test, and BPG Heteroscedasticity Test

Country	Lags	LM Autocorrelation Test (Prob.)	BPG Heteroscedasticity Test (Prob.)
G1 Exp EUA	(1,0,0)	1.464884 (0.2369)	0.347831 (0.7908)
G2 Exp EUA°	(1,0,4)	0.778582 (0.4626)	2.793509 (0.0199)
G3 Exp EUA	(1,4,0)	0.113151 (0.8932)	0.375645 (0.9305)
G4 Exp EUA	(1,1,2)	0.191549 (0.8261)	1.385602 (0.2301)
G5 Exp EUA	(2,1,2)	1.686001 (0.1918)	0.927048 (0.4902)
G8 Exp EUA	(1,0,2)	0.420410 (0.6582)	1.031426 (0.4046)
G10 Exp EUA	(4,0,1)	0.116159 (0.8905)	0.850679 (0.5614)
G11 Exp EUA	(1,3,5)	0.013135 (0.987)	1.462197 (0.164)
G13 Exp EUA	(6,4,0)	0.211176 (0.8102)	0.557335 (0.8887)
G2 Imp EUA	(4,1,4)	0.153650 (0.8578)	0.578935 (0.8402)
G4 Imp EUA	(4,4,3)	1.800128 (0.1727)	1.205222 (0.2905)
G5 Imp EUA	(5,0,0)	0.459923 (0.6331)	1.806683 (0.0883)
G7 Imp EUA	(5,5,2)	0.318263 (0.7285)	0.563818 (0.9002)
G9 Imp EUA	(2,0,0)	0.159315 (0.853)	1.079982 (0.3716)
G10 Imp EUA	(1,4,0)	0.056145 (0.9454)	0.589712 (0.7625)
G11 Imp EUA	(4,4,6)	0.533832 (0.5889)	1.643098 (0.0741)
G12 Imp EUA°	(1,5,6)	0.040605 (0.9602)	2.013648 (0.0286)
G3 Exp China	(1,0,0)	1.335813 (0.2685)	1.462159 (0.2108)
G4 Exp China°	(2,4,2)	0.294202 (0.7461)	3.352353 (0.0007)
G5 Exp China	(5,0,0)	0.800470 (0.4528)	1.636999 (0.1372)
G10 Exp China	(2,0,4)	0.294802 (0.7455)	0.967423 (0.4675)
G11 Exp China	(1,5,2)	1.641965 (0.2007)	1.569019 (0.1257)
G12 Exp China‡	(5,6,4)	2.482961 (0.0913)	2.146749 (0.0140)
G3 Imp China	(2,0,0)	2.058458 (0.1341)	1.372046 (0.2505)
G5 Imp China	(1,3,2)	0.614718 (0.5434)	1.345311 (0.2276)
G10 Imp China°	(4,3,6)	0.136628 (0.8725)	1.729262 (0.0613)
G10 Exp Hol	(2,6,0)	1.076018 (0.3463)	0.699479 (0.7219)

G13 Exp Hol	(1,0,0)	0.094246 (0.9102)	0.904716 (0.4650)
G2 Imp Hol	(1,0,0)	1.527255 (0.2230)	0.625367 (0.6005)
G3 Imp Hol	(1,0,0)	0.604919 (0.5485)	1.180671 (0.3255)
G5 Imp Hol	(1,0,0)	0.242013 (0.7856)	1.446952 (0.2347)
G8 Imp Hol ^o	(1,0,0)	1.338573 (0.2678)	2.556843 (0.0332)
G11 Imp Hol	(1,0,2)	0.002813 (0.9972)	1.640646 (0.1462)
G12 Imp Hol	(2,4,0)	0.731383 (0.4846)	1.608903 (0.1356)

* Order of the variables: Imports (or Exports), GDP, and Exchange Rate.

LM test performed with 2 lags.

^o Model estimated with White's covariance matrix.

‡ Model estimated with HAC covariance matrix.

Models with restricted constant, selected using the Akaike criterion and a maximum of 6 lags.

Source: Results obtained by the authors from Eviews 10